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THE IMPLICATION AND IMPACT OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST) ON INDIAN ECONOMY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANUFACTURING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

GST also known as the Goods and Services Tax is defined as the giant indirect tax structure designed to support and enhance the economic growth of a country. Across the Globe more than 150 countries have implemented and executed GST. In India the idea of GST was from the year 2000 during Vajpayee's government. GST was finally constituted and passed in the year 2016. It is considered to be a totally game changer for the countries economic condition and there is lot of expectation from its implication and execution. GST is comprehensive tax mechanism where in all major indirect taxes are clubbed into one, whether they are levied on services(service tax) or goods(excise and vat). It will reduce the compliance burdens, and would be very transparent for the tax payers and collectors. The major benefit of introducing GST is to reduce the cascading effects of taxes. It is interesting to study the impact of GST in the Indian economy after the demonetizations of the currency because there is a predication of slow down in the Indian economy and globally as well. The current government which passed the GST bill is confident that it can turn around the manufacturing sectors which is very slow compared to other sectors with implication of GST. The another positive effect of this tax structure is to curb inflation and to make direct and indirect commodities cheaper so that countries economic growth is decent. The purpose of this paper is to analyse the implication and impact of GST and to examine the deeper research opportunities in this area. This paper is a descriptive study where the study is based on past economic scenario of the country and how the new GST regime will change World's second largest growing economy.

Keywords: Goods and service Tax, Indian economy and manufacturing sector.

Introduction:

The word **tax** is derived from the Latin word, 'taxare' meaning 'to estimate'. "A tax is not a voluntary payment or donation, but an enforced contribution, exacted pursuant to legislative authority" and is any contribution imposed by government whether under the name of toll, tribute, impost, duty, custom, excise, subsidy, aid, supply, or other name."¹ The first known system of taxation was in Ancient Egypt around 3000 BC - 2800 BC in the first dynasty of the Old Kingdom. Records from that time show that the pharaoh would conduct a biennial tour of the kingdom, collecting tax revenues from the people. Other records are granary receipts on limestone flakes and papyrus. Early taxation is also described in the Bible. In Genesis², it states "But when the crop comes in, give a fifth of it to Pharaoh. The other four-fifths you may keep as seed for the fields and as food for yourselves and your households and your children." Joseph was telling the people of Egypt how to divide their crop, providing a portion to the Pharaoh. A share 3 of the crop was the tax.

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a vast concept that simplifies the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturing, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level [1]. The Goods and Services Tax Bill or GST Bill, also referred to as The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Second Amendment) Bill, 2014, initiates a Value added Tax to be implemented on a national level in India. GST will be an indirect tax at all the stages of production to bring about uniformity in the system. On bringing GST into practice, there would be amalgamation of Central and State taxes into a single tax payment. It would also enhance the position of India in both, domestic as well as international market. At the consumer level, GST would reduce the overall tax burden, which is currently estimated at 25-30%. Under this system, the consumer pays the final tax but an efficient input tax credit system ensures that there is no cascading of taxes- tax on tax paid on inputs that go into manufacture of goods [2]. In order to avoid the payment of multiple taxes such as excise duty and service tax at Central level and VAT at the State level, GST would unify these taxes and create a uniform market throughout the country. Integration of various taxes into a GST system will bring about an effective cross-utilization of credits. The current system taxes production, whereas the GST will aim to tax consumption.

Importance of GST in India

Experts have enlisted the benefits of GST as under:

- It would introduce two-tiered One-Country-One-Tax regime.
- It would subsume all indirect taxes at the centre and the state level.

- It would not only widen the tax regime by covering goods and services but also make it transparent.
- It would free the manufacturing sector from cascading effect of taxes, thus by improve the cost-competitiveness of goods and services.
- It would bring down the prices of goods and services and thus by, increase consumption.
- It would create business-friendly environment, thus by increase tax-GDP ratio
- It would enhance the ease of doing business in India.uld enhance the ease of doing business in India.

Wall Street firm Goldman Sachs, in a note 'India: Q and A on GST Growth Impact Could Be Muted', has put out estimates that show that the Modi Government's model for the Goods and Services Tax (GST) will not raise growth, will push up consumer prices inflation and may not result in increased tax revenue collections. There appears to be certain loopholes in the proposed GST tax regime which may be detrimental in delivering the desired results. They are:

India has adopted dual GST instead of national GST. It has made the entire structure of GST fairly complicated in India. The centre will have to coordinate with 29 states and 7 union territories to implement such tax regime. Such regime is likely to create economic as well as political issues. The states are likely to lose the say in determining rates once GST is implemented. The sharing of revenues between the states and the centre is still a matter of contention with no consensus arrived regarding revenue neutral rate.

Chief Economic Advisor Arvind Subramanian on 4 December 2015 suggested GST rates of 12% for concessional goods, 17-18% for standard goods and 40% for luxury goods which is much higher than the present maximum service tax rate of 14%. Such initiative is likely to push inflation The proposed GST structure is likely to succeed only if the country has a strong IT network. It is a well-known fact that India is still in the budding state as far as internet connectivity is concerned. Moreover, the proposed regime seems to ignore the emerging sector of e-commerce. E-commerce does not leave signs of the transaction outside the internet and has anonymity associated with it. As a result, it becomes almost impossible to track the business transaction taking place through internet which can be business to business, business to customer or customer to customer. Again, there appears to be no clarity as to whether a product should be considered a service or a product under the concept of E-commerce. New techniques can be developed to track such transactions but until such technologies become readily accessible, generation of tax revenue from this sector would continue to be uncertain and much below the expectation. Again E-commerce has been insulated against taxation under custom duty moratorium on electronic transmissions by the

WTO Bali Ministerial Conference held in 2014 .Communication is considered to be necessity and one cannot do without communication. In modern times, communication has assumed the dimension of telecommunication.

One of the major drawbacks of the GST regime could be the direct spike in the service tax rate from 14% to 20-22%” (GST: Impact on the Telecommunications Sector in India). The proposed GST appears to be silent on whether telecommunication can be considered under the category of goods or services. The entire issue of telecommunication sector assumes a serious proportion when India’s rural tele density is not even 50%.It is a well-known fact that petroleum products have been a major contributor to inflation in India. Inflation in India depends on how the government intends to include petroleum products under GST in future.

Electricity is essential for the growth and development of India. If electricity is included under standard or luxury goods in future then it would badly affect the development of India. It is said that GST would impact negatively on the real estate market. It would add up to 8% to the cost of new homes and reduce demand by about 12%.

This would give the governments the access to substantial incremental revenues since this industry has historically been tax free in its entirety”. It sounds ridiculous but the provision of GST is likely to make the supervision of operations by its Board/senior managers across the company’s offices in different parts of the country a taxable service by allowing each state to raise a GST demand on the company Again there appears to be lack of consensus over fixing the revenue rate as well as threshold limit. One thing is for sure, services in India are going to be steeply costly if GST is fixed above the present service tax rate of 14% which in turn will spiral up inflation in India. “Asian countries which implemented GST all had witnessed retail inflation in the year of implementation.

Conclusion:

The proposed GST regime is a half-hearted attempt to rationalize indirect tax structure. More than 150 countries have implemented GST. The government of India should study the GST regime set up by various countries and also their fallouts before implementing it. At the same time, the government should make an attempt to insulate the vast poor population of India against the likely inflation due to implementation of GST. No doubt, GST will simplify existing indirect tax system and will help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous taxation system only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate, and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor and real

estate. Until the consensus is reached, the government should resist from implementing such regime. The taxation of goods and services in India has, hitherto, been characterized as a cascading and distortionary tax on production resulting in mis-allocation of resources and lower productivity and economic growth. It also inhibits voluntary compliance. It is well recognized that this problem can be effectively addressed by shifting the tax burden from production and trade to final consumption. A well designed destination-based value added tax on all goods and services is the most elegant method of eliminating distortions and taxing consumption. Under this structure, all different stages of production and distribution can be interpreted as a mere tax pass-through, and the tax essentially 'sticks' on final consumption within the taxing jurisdiction. A 'flawless' GST in the context of the federal structure which would optimize efficiency, equity and effectiveness. The 'flawless' GST is designed as a consumption type destination VAT based on invoice-credit method.

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